

EFFECT OF PARENTS' SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS ON SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN HAMISI SUB-COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract:

The joy of parents, teachers and students lies in high academic achievement attained by students in their national examinations. To the student this marks the beginning of lucrative careers studied at the universities. To the parents, such children are bound to change their socio-economic life once employed while the teachers might be assured of promotions. This study's purpose was to address the problem of students posting lower test scores in secondary schools compared to their initial performance at the primary school's KCPE. It focused on analyzing effect of parent's socio-economic status on students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Hamisi sub-county, Vihiga – Kenya with focus on students who score high grades in primary school's KCPE vis-à-vis what they achieve at KCSE. The specific objective addressed was: To ascertain the socio-economic factors contributing to students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county Vihiga county – Kenya. The study employed descriptive survey research design. The target population was 4,298 with 41 Principals, 428 teachers, 3826 students, 1 DEO and 2 AEOs. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the DEO. Simple random sampling was used to select the teachers, students and the AEO. The sample size was 525 respondents consisting of 12 principals, 128 teachers, 383 students, one DEO and one AEO. Data collection tools used were structured and unstructured questionnaires, interview schedules and document analysis. Instrument validity was done through content validity whereas the test and re-test technique was used to test the reliability of the tools comparing with a Pearson

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Correlation Coefficient of 0.5. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics hence Quantitative data were presented using frequency counts, means and percentages with the aid of the SPSS Version 16.0. Qualitative data were analyzed thematically. Triangulation strategy was used to merge findings from both qualitative and quantitative for presentation using for instance frequency distribution tables, bar graphs, pie charts and verbatim. It came to light that students receded academically at the secondary schooling level due to low parents' socio-economic status. A few from well-endowed families attained favorable scores. It was recommended that the government should create an enabling environment for parents to be self-employed so that they cater for their children's educational needs such as the subsidized school fees. It is hoped that this research's findings will inform Hamisi sub-county Education Office and the Ministry of Education Science and Technology at large in their policy formulation and implementation in this era of Education For All (EFA).

Keywords: parent, career, triangulation, implementation, socio-economic, academic achievement

1. Background of Study

A worrying students' academic achievement trend in public secondary schools in Hamisi sub-county was discovered. It was found that students tended to recede academically once they got admitted to secondary schools from primary schools. A survey of student academic achievement of 4, 265 students in 13 randomly selected secondary schools in Hamisi sub-county reveals this trend. Figure 1 shows the achievement of the students in primary school's KCPE while the next figure shows the respective achievement of secondary school's KCSE. See the figures 1 and 2 below.

Figure 1: KCPE Academic Achievement (2011 – 2014)
Source: Fieldwork (2015)

Figure 2: KCSE Academic Achievements (2011 – 2014)

Information in Figure 1 above indicate that out of the total number of students who wrote their KCSE examination in schools in Hamisi sub-county, 222(71.4%) had scored a C+ and above in their KCPE. However, four years later and upon writing their KCSE examination, only 105(33.8%) managed to score a C+ or above (see figure 2). This in itself was a drastic drop in academic achievement of these very students. This means that the larger percentage i.e. 206(66.2%) did not make it to university for failing to qualify by scoring the minimum entry requirement grade of at least a C+ at KCSE.

The researcher was of the belief that poor socio-economic status (SES) of parents/guardians could have been a contributing factor to the students' academic achievement in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education. In view of the costs involved in educating a child, the individual costs such as: purchase of books, fee payment, the opportunity cost and the societal costs such as: paying salaries for teachers and training of teachers, education is an entirely very expensive venture (Chiuri and Kiumi, 2005).

Considine and Zappala (2002) noted in their study in Australia that children from humble or less affluent families with meagre income will depict models in terms of learning such as; low literacy ranking, very low retention rates, problems with their school behaviour and difficulties in their studies caused by negative attitudes towards learning. UNESCO (2015) and Shoukat et al., (2013) who cited Eamon (2005) put it that students from low socio-economic status and rural areas show dismal academic studies as evidenced in their low test scores as compared to the more affluent mates. Such students come last in case of educational benefits like aid. The level of parent's/guardian's education is important to their children. Wasanga and Kyala (2007) note that in most cases, children whose parents have attained some education are likely to benefit from greater parental support than those who do not have an education. Parents who strain to buy food in the home will find it even harder to forego food purchases – if in a sporadic position – and pay fees for their children. Such children will not attend school and if part of the fees is paid, then other needs such as books, uniforms will be demanding from the already over-stretched parents/guardians. These students' basic needs will remain unfulfilled hence fail to perform academically, (Farooq et. al., 2011).

Several studies as observed by Jeynes (2002) have also found out the social status of a parent or a guardian affects a child positively or negatively in his/her academics. If a parent has a high academic and professional qualification topped with an inclined occupational affiliation, their children will perform better than the other children whose parents the researcher will call 'commoners'. Graetz (1995) in his own study observed that a student's education success is heavily dependent on the social status of his/her parents/guardians in the society. Kibera and Kimokoti (2007) put it that there are as many different kinds of education as there are social classes. The social status of a person affects his perceptions about value of life including education while Malinda

(2015) cited Christopher B. Forest as having found in his 2013 study that children who claim a high satisfaction in life and are in optimal health maintain greater connection with teachers, earn high grades and are more committed to schoolwork. Such students are the ones from the elevated social class – it has been noted. Gakuru (1997) said that the high-to-do families take their children to school earlier and these schools are usually the best. This is because they have the financial clout to do this. However, low SES level of parents obstructs individuals from gaining access to sources and resources of learning. This negatively affects their academic achievement (Eamon, 2005; Lopez, 1995 and Farooq et al. 2011)

On a contradictory note, however, Ali Shoukat et al., (2013) sites Pedrosa et al., (2006) in whose study they found out those students from socio-economic homesteads which are deprived perform better than those from higher socio-economically and educationally endowed areas. With this, Ali deduced that the criterion for categorization of socio-economic standards varies with countries (counties) depending on their norms and values. In this case, criteria for gauging low socio-economic status shall be different for developed countries in relation to the developing ones. Though Farooq et al., (2011) in their study found out positive significant effect on students' academic achievement due to parents'/guardians' level of education, they also deduced from the same study that parents'/guardians' occupation had no effect on the same variable.

The home environment may contribute negatively or positively to students' academic achievement or vice versa. In this sense, educated parents/guardians will provide that environment that suits best for academic success of their children (Farooq et al. 2011). These parents will deeply get involved with their children's academics. End result? The children will score higher in standardized examinations than their counterparts whose parents are uneducated (Kranshen, 2005). These parents are better communicators of school work and activities and have the ability to help their children academically (Fantuzzo and Tighe, 2000). Betsy (2015) insisted that parents should play a leading role in their children's education. This can be through cooperation with the school through attending meetings, getting to know their children's teachers and guide the children in doing homework apart from creating a conducive environment for the same. The researcher had the belief that an educated parent will do this effortlessly and thus enable the child to perform better in his/her academics.

2. Statement of the Problem

Parents/guardians to students in primary schools will always be enthusiastic of the high prospects of their children once they join secondary school. The bar for academic achievement is set even higher when the children attain highly at the final primary

schooling national examination. The case of secondary school students' academic achievement in Hamisi sub-county paints a negative picture as outlined in the background of this study. Students who excel in primary schools end up receding academically at the final secondary school summative examination.

Many factors could be playing to this but the researcher sought to analyse the impact of socio-economic status of the parents/guardians to their students' academic achievement in Hamisi sub-county, Vihiga – Kenya.

3. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to analyze the effect of parents' socio-economic status on students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county, Vihiga County - Kenya with specific attention on high performing students in primary school who could not return a higher grade in secondary school.

3.1 Research Objectives

This study was guided by the following objective:

- To ascertain the socio-economic factors contributing to students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county, Vihiga county – Kenya

3.2 Research questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

- What are the socio-economic factors contributing to students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county?

4. Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) opine that descriptive survey design is a way of collecting information by interviewing or issuing questionnaires to sampled individuals. They assert that it is an efficient method of collecting large amounts of information. Both qualitative and quantitative data will be sought and manipulated accordingly.

4.1 Target Population

This study targeted 41 public secondary schools within the sub-county which had been presenting candidates for the KCSE examination for the past four years (2011-2014). In addition, a total of 3,826 students (both boys and girls), 41 Principals, one DEO and two

AEO's in Hamisi sub-county also participated in the study. The summary is as in table 1 below. In total the research targeted 4,298 respondents.

Table 1: Target Population

Divisions	Schools	Principals	Teachers	Students	DEO	AEO
Tiriki West	24	24	251	2581		1
Tiriki East	17	17	177	1245		1
Totals	41	41	428	3826	1	2

(N = 4,298)

Source: DEO's Office, 2015

4.2 Sample size and sampling procedures

The researcher used simple random sampling to select 12 public secondary schools, 12 Principals, 128 teachers and 383 former secondary school students (years 2011-2014). The use of simple random sampling was applied because it gives each member of a population an equal chance of being selected (Kombo and Tromp, 2000). Stratified random sampling was used to classify public secondary schools into two divisions. These homogeneous sub-groups so created allowed for proportional representation of the population sub-groups (Kombo and Tromp, 2000). Purposive sampling procedure was used to select one District Education Officer (DEO). One Area Education Officer (AEO) was selected using simple random sampling. Naisuma's (2000) Coefficient of variation was used to select sample size of public secondary schools, teachers and students .The sample size of between 20%-30% is same as that proposed by Best and Khan (2003). Such sample size is ideal in providence of reliable data when selected randomly. Therefore, in this study, the schools, Principals and teachers was selected using the figure recommended above. For the students, Kombo and Tromp (2000) recommendation of a 10% - 30% sample size was used. Table 2 shows the sample use in this study. See the table.

Table 2: Sample size

Divisions	Schools	Principals	Teachers	Students	DEO	AEO
Tiriki West	7	7	75	258	1	1
Tiriki East	5	5	53	125		1
Totals	12	12	128	383	1	1

(n=525)

Source: Hamisi Sub-county DEO's Office, 2015.

4.3 Data Collection Tools

The researcher used questionnaires, interviews and document analysis.

4.4 Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

Kombo and Tromp (2000) define validity of a tool as a measure of how well a tool measures what it is supposed to measure. Whereas Test and retest technique was used to achieve reliability of the tools, expert knowledge from lecturers from Mount Kenya University, Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology and Egerton University was sought to achieve high validity of data collection instruments.

4.5 Data Collection and Analysis

The researcher prepared and then delivered questionnaires on the agreed date to the respondents and allowed sufficient time before going back to collect them. The researcher liaised with the principals so that s/he posted to or invited some of the students to school for purposes of filling in in the questionnaires. On the day of the questionnaire collection, the researcher carried out interviews with the principals while that for the DEO and AEO was done on a separate date. All respondents were assured of the highest degree of confidentiality with which data provided by them was to be treated. Collected data were analyzed categorically in which case Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics hence results presented using frequency counts, means and percentages with the aid of the SPSS Version 24.0. Qualitative data was analyzed thematically hence results of data analysis were presented in form of frequency distribution tables, bar graphs, and pie charts.

5. Findings and Discussions

5.1 Gender of Respondents

There were more male teachers than females ones in that 67(55.4%) represented males while 54(44.6%) were females. This disparity was seen also with principals because 3 (25.0%) were females while 9 (75.0%) were males. The two education officers (DEO and AEO) were male. For students, males stood higher at 182(58.4%) while the female student number was 129(41.6%). Figure 3 shows the gender distribution of the respondents who took part in the study.

Figure 3: Gender Distribution of the Respondents (2011 – 2014)

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

The higher number of male students than female can be attributed to several factors among them, as research done in Kenya and Ghana shows, the tendency of girls being more likely to drop out of school than boys because of negative attitudes and discrimination (Sutherland-Addy et al, 1995).

5.2 Age of respondents

Data collected on respondents' ages was as depicted in the tables below. Table 3 shows the age brackets of principals, teachers, the DEO and the AEO while table 4 shows the age brackets of the students who took part in this study. See the tables below.

Table 3: Age of Respondents – Principals, Teachers, DEO and AEO

Category of Respondents	Age brackets				Total
	30 or below	30 - 39	40 - 49	50 or above	
Principals	0 (0.0%)	3 (25%)	5 (41.7%)	4 (33.3%)	12 (100%)
Teachers	38 (31.4%)	47 (38.9%)	31(25.6%)	5(4.1%)	121(100%)
DEO	-	-	1 (100%)	-	-
AEO	-	-	1 (100%)	-	-

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

Table 4: Age of Respondents – Students

Age Bracket	15 – 17	18 – 19	20 – 21	Above 21	Total
No. of Students	24(7.7%)	190 (61.1%)	61(19.6%)	36 (11.6%)	311 (100%)

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

Most principals, 5(41.7%), were aged between 40 – 49 years while 3(25%) principals had their age lying within bracket 30 – 39 years. There was no any principal whose age was below 30 while 4(33.3%) principals had their ages at 50 or above. As a consequence, it was ideal to note that all the principals were mature individuals whose median age

revolved at around 40 - 49 years. Maria et al. (2007) note adults (persons above 26 years) have developed varied and sophisticated ways to contrast the elements that affect a decision. This could be the result of past exposure and experiences. It should therefore be noted that the ages of the principals put them in a better place to lead the schools in Hamisi sub-county well. On the side of teachers, 38 (31.4%) were aged 30 years and below. A total of 47(38.9%) had ages between 30 – 40 years, 31 (25.6%) had ages between 40 – 49 years. 5(4.1%) teachers were aged above 50 years. For students, 24(7.7%) were aged between 15 – 17 years. A total of 190 (61.1%) were between 18 – 19 years of age with a total of 61 or (19.6%) falling in the 20 – 21 age bracket. Finally 36 students, 11.6%, were above 21 years of age at the time they did their KCSE. Both the DEO and the AEO had their ages between 40 – 49 years.

5.3 Parents'/Guardians' Educational level

The students were asked to fill in in the questionnaires regarding the level of their parents'/ guardian's education. The data collected on this issue was highlighted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Parents'/Guardians Educational level

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

Figure 3 above indicate the educational level of the parents/guardians to the students in Hamisi Sub-county's 2011 – 2014 secondary school candidate classes. The data showed that most of the parents 124(39.9%) had secondary school level education. This was followed by those with primary school level of education at 101(32.5%). A further 48(15.4%), however, had college level education with a mere 9(2.9%) of the parents/guardians with university education. A worrying 29(9.3%) of the parents/guardians did not have any formal education, it occurred to the researchers. With a combined 254(81.7%) of the parents/guardians having secondary school-level education or below to no education at all, it was widely not expected for this parents to understand much insofar helping their children academically was concerned. In this case, these less educated parents/guardians as postulated by Farooq et al. (2011) failed

to provide that environment that suits best for academic success of their children. These parents could not get deeply involved with their children's academics leading to low academic achievement. Those students whose parents had had better education beyond secondary school were likely to guide their children through thus enable them to achieve higher academically.

5.4 Parents'/Guardians' Employment Status

The employment status of the parents/guardians to the students who did their KCSE examination during the research period 2011 – 2014 was sought by the researcher. The economic activities mentioned were restricted to salaried jobs which not only earns a worker a salary but also prestige. This ups their social standing with the effects trickling down to their children's academic work positively (Graetz, 1995). The respondents' responses on Parents'/Guardians' Employment Status was as shown in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Employment Status

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

The researcher also sought to know whether parents/guardians had a job from which they could derive a salary/wage to foot bills including the education of their children. The data revealed that 90(28.9%) represented students' families where only one of the parents had a job while 185(59.5%) represented families in which both parents were jobless. The smallest percentage of 36(11.6%) represented families in which both parents had jobs.

With the above information, the researcher sought to find out whether the parents/guardians provided essential academic help, resources or facilities given the perceived challenge they were experiencing. The table below shows data collected from respondents' regarding provision of essential needs/help for students' academics. See the table 5 below.

Table 5: Students' Responses on Socio-Economic Issues

Issue	SA (5)	A (4)	UD (3)	DA (2)	SD (1)
I was provided with enough personal school items by parents/guardian e.g. uniform, pocket money etc.	[23] 7.4%	[39] 12.5%	[23] 7.4%	[149] 47.9%	[77] 24.8%
I had sufficient reading materials at home including a good room for studying.	[14] 4.5%	[26] 8.4%	[35] 11.3%	[141] 45.3%	[95] 30.5%
My parents would help/support me do homework.	[9] 2.9%	[12] 3.9%	[41] 13.2%	[80] 25.7%	[169] 54.3%
My parent/guardian attended and participated actively in school meetings and academic days.	[33] 10.6%	[41] 13.2%	[47] 15.1%	[103] 33.1%	[87] 28.0%
Fee payment was a problem that led to me being frequently sent home.	[105] 33.8%	[96] 30.9%	[32] 10.3%	[53] 17.0%	[25] 8.0%

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

All these requirements were deemed vital for the students' learning in order that they post high academic achievement. On provision of enough personal school items such as uniforms and pocket money, 149(47.9%) of the students disagreed saying that they did not get these resources. A further 77(24.8%) strongly disagreed with 23(7.4%) being undecided on the issue. 39(12.5%) and 23(7.4%), however, agreed and strongly agreed that they received the resources. Going by Farooq et al. (2011), these students were bound to perform dismally in academics for non-providence of personal items including uniforms and pocket money by their parents/guardians.

Regarding reading materials, 141(45.3%) of the student respondents disagreed, 95(30.5%) strongly disagreed to having sufficient reading materials with a good study at home while 35(11.3%) were undecided. The researcher also sought to know whether parents/guardians supported their children at home with academic work such as homework. The student painted a picture depicting that parents/guardians did not offer this kind of help in that 169(54.3%) and 80(25.7%) of the students were adamant that parents helped them out with homework by strongly disagreeing and disagreeing respectively. Only 9(2.9%) and 12(3.9%) received academic tutoring from parents with the former percentage strongly agreeing while the latter agreeing. This finding was in synchrony with the educational level of the parents/guardians which, as observed above, revealed a total of 254(81.7%) of the parents had Secondary school level education and below or none at all. Such parents felt less confident in helping their children out with their academic work. Another 41(13.2%) were undecided. Conversely, parents seemed to avoid attending school meeting and academic days as seen by 103(33.1%) of the student respondents disagreeing to the statement and 28.0% strongly disagreeing. Only 33(10.6%) strongly agreed to have their parents/guardians attending these meetings while 41(13.2%) agreed to the same. The remaining 47(15.1%) of the respondents were undecided. As regards fee payment, a large percentage, 105(33.8%), of the student respondents strongly agreed that they were sent home from school due

to inability of their parents/guardians to pay fees. 96(30.9%) also still agreed to the same issue. Only 25(8.0%) and 53(17.0%) strongly disagreed and disagreed flatly that fee payment was a problem to their parents/guardians – they were not sent home for the same. This information was in tandem with the parents'/guardians' economic activities that showed that 185(59.5%) (Figure 4.8) of them did not have jobs at all and thus the strain in fee payment. The remaining 32(10.3%) were undecided on the same issue.

The teachers were also asked questions on the above aspects. Data collected revealed a trend almost akin to that of the student respondents in that 51(42.1%) of this group of respondents agreed that parents/guardians provided enough relevant reading materials to their children. This implied that a higher percentage of 57.9 % (70) of the students did not receive these vital resources as per the teachers. A larger number of them also, 71(58.7%), gave a No answer to the query: 'Are students provided with enough personal school items e.g. School uniform and books etc. by parents hence making them comfortable in school?' This communicated the fact that students had to make do without such important things. A total of 19 of the teacher respondents constituting 15.7% denoted in the comment section that teaching literature was a problem given that students did not have the required novels, novellas or plays. On attending school academic days for their children, most teachers still (74 or 61.2%) gave a No answer implying that parents/guardians did not attend academic days of their children. A total of 52(43.0%) affirmed that parents attended their children's school academic days.

The principals, on the other hand, were asked through interviews whether parents supported school programmes. Most of them, 10(83.3%) precisely, replied in the negative. They, however, blamed poverty and low self-esteem as causes of parents shunning school meetings. Poverty was blamed on the inability of parents to pay school fees for their children. During meetings, the few parents and guardians who came did not participate actively. They tended to be consumers of schools legislation as opposed to makers of the same.

Most parents attending will arrive late for the meetings and sit through those meetings. They will not utter a single word. They can be serious agents of rubberstamping poor policies by rogue principals for they say many yeses than critiquing issues' one principal observed.

A small number, 2(16.7%), of the principals said that parents paid fees in time and were very supportive of the school programmes.

Both the DEO and the AEO opined that many parents in Hamisi sub-county were poverty-stricken and thus strained to pay school fees for their children. Their children, consequently, missed valuable time as a result when sent home for fees. The parents were not also able to provide for other requirements for the students. It should be noted that in spite of the introduction of Free Secondary Education (FSE) in Kenya in

2008, parents are still required to pay levies such as PTA fund and lunch fee as these are not factored in the FSE package. In an address at Kisii High School in Kenya, the President of the Republic of Kenya promised that his government would provide completely free secondary education by 2016 (PSCU, 2014). By this statement, the president acknowledged that secondary education in Kenya was not free as some people thought thus the agony the parents went through educating their children and hence low or worse still a receding academic achievement of the learners.

5.5 Summary of the Major Findings

It was found out that 101(32.5%) and 124(39.9%) of the parents/guardians had primary and secondary level education respectively. Another 48(15.4%) had college education and 9(2.9%) had university education. A further 29(9.3%) did not have any education at all. The job status of parents was also sought in which case 36(11.6%) of the student respondents said that both their parents had jobs while 185(59.5%) said that none of their parents/guardians had a job. It was found out that 38.9 % (90) of the students came from families where only one parent had a job.

On provision of personal school items, a combined total of 226(72.7%) of students said they were not provided with these items. Only 62(19.9%) agreed to receiving the items. A similar case was with provision of sufficient reading materials at home in that 141(45.3%) of the students disagreed while 95(30.5%) strongly disagreed implying that they did not have reading materials at home including a study. A mere combined figure of 40(12.9%) of the students agreed to having the resources. Parents/guardians did not support students with homework at home as seen by the 169(54.3%) who disagreed with the statement that they received help. Only 9(2.9%) said they received this help. Many parents did not attend school meetings and academic days. A combined 190(61.1%) saying their parents did not attend the meetings. This was supported by 81(60.8%) of the teachers. Many parents/guardians struggled paying school fees since 105(33.8%) and 96(30.9%) of the students got sent home frequently due to fee arrears. This was over 60% of all the students.

Data collected from teachers revealed a trend almost akin to that of the student respondents in that 51(42.1%) of the teachers agreed that parents/guardians provided enough relevant reading materials to their children. This implied that a higher percentage of 57.9 % (70) of the teachers informed that the students did not receive these vital resources. A larger number of them also, 71(58.5%), gave a No answer to the query: 'Are students provided with enough personal school items e.g. School uniform and books etc. by parents hence making them comfortable in school?' This communicated the fact that students had to make do without such important things. A total of 19 of the teacher respondents constituting 15.7% denoted in the comment section that teaching literature was a problem given that students did not have the

required novels, novellas or plays. On attending school academic days for their children, most teachers still (74 or 61.2%) gave a No answer implying that parents/guardians did not attend academic days of their children. A total of 52(43.0%) affirmed that parents attended their children's school academic days.

Most of the principals, 10(83.3%) precisely, replied in the negative. They, however, blamed poverty and low self-esteem as causes of parents shunning school meetings. A small number, 2(16.7%), of the principals said that parents paid fees in time and were very supportive of the school programmes.

Both the DEO and the AEO opined that many parents in Hamisi sub-county were poverty-stricken and thus strained to pay school fees for their children. Their children, consequently, missed valuable time as a result when sent home for fees.

6. Conclusions

1. Students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Hamisi sub-county is very low. That these secondary schools do not add value to many of the students who get admitted there from primary school. Put simply, students get admitted with high grades but fail to replicate these grades at the secondary schools' KCSE examination.
2. Most parents did not have worthwhile education since some of them had never gone to school while others had primary level education. A few had secondary level education. The numbers for college and university graduates among the parents was limited.
3. As a result of weak educational background, most parents/guardians did not have jobs with more than 50.0% being jobless. They could neither, therefore, help their children academically at home nor pay fees effortlessly.

7. Recommendations

1. The government should sensitize parents on how to care for their secondary school-going children with the aim of giving them ample time to study, providing necessities and attending meetings at school.
2. The government should create an enabling environment for parents/guardians to be self-employed so that they may cater for their children's educational needs.
3. The subsidized tuition-free secondary education should be entirely free to ease the burden of fee payment from parents thus make students stay focused in school without interruption of being sent for fees.

4. The government, through the Ministry of Education, should ensure that Adult and Continuing Education (ACE) and Non-formal Education (NFE) programmes are active and enhanced with capacity to help solve the problem of the uneducated adults.

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